

Thermodynamics of Amino Acid Ionisation in Aqueous Solutions using pH-Titration

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The ionisation constants of L-serine, L-phenylalanine and L-proline in aqueous solution have been determined potentiometrically using Bjerrum's technique at wide range of ionic strengths (0.07–0.32 M) and temperatures (25–45°). Thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have also been calculated.

The ionisation constants of amino acids have been studied by several authors. Most of previous studies were carried out at only one ionic strength and at a selected temperature^{1–6}. To gain a complete picture of the ionisation equilibria for L-serine, L-phenylalanine and L-proline, our measurements were carried out at a wide range of ionic strengths ($\mu = 0.07, 0.12, 0.17, 0.22$ and $0.32 M$) and temperatures (25, 30, 35, 40 and 45°). The ionisation constants of these amino acids have been determined potentiometrically using Bjerrum's technique⁷.

Calculations :

For calculating the ionisation constants of the studied amino acids, we consider the following equilibria (choosing L-serine as example for simplicity) :

The equilibrium defined by (1) and (2) predominates at $\text{pH} < 7$.

Also

Here again, the equilibrium defined by (3) and (4) predominates at $\text{pH} > 7$.

(a) Titration with HClO_4 permits determination of K_1 by applying charge balance and mass balance equations to the system given by equation (1) as follows :

$$\text{Charge balance : } [\text{ClO}_4^-] + [\text{OH}^-] = [\text{H}_2\text{A}^+] + [\text{H}^+] \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Mass balance : } A_{\text{tot}} = \text{H}_2\text{A}^+ + \text{HA} \quad (6)$$

On combining (5), (6) and (2), we obtain

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{H}^+] \left(A_{\text{tot}} - \{ [\text{ClO}_4^-] + [\text{OH}^-] - [\text{H}^+] \} \right)}{[\text{ClO}_4^-] + [\text{OH}^-] - [\text{H}^+]} \quad (7)$$

and hence

$$\text{p}K_1 = -\log_{10}[\text{H}^+] + \log_{10} \frac{[\text{ClO}_4^-] + [\text{OH}^-] - [\text{H}^+]}{A_{\text{tot}} - [\text{ClO}_4^-] - [\text{OH}^-] + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (8)$$

(b) Also titration with NaOH permits determination of K_2 by applying similar equations on the system defined by equation (3),

$$\text{Charge balance : } [\text{H}^+] + [\text{Na}^+] = [\text{OH}^-] + [\text{A}^-] \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Mass balance : } A_{\text{tot}} = \text{HA} + \text{A}^- \quad (10)$$

On combining (9), (10) and (4), we get

$$K_2 = \frac{[H^+]\left([H^+] + [Na^+] - [OH^-]\right)}{A_{tot} - \left([H^+] + [Na^+] - [OH^-]\right)} \quad (11)$$

and

$$pK_2 = -\log_{10}[H^+] + \log_{10} \frac{A_{tot} - \left([H^+] + [Na^+] - [OH^-]\right)}{[H^+] + [Na^+] - [OH^-]} \quad (12)$$

where, A_{tot} is the total amino acid concentration.

Final values of pK_1 and pK_2 were obtained from the negative logarithm of the final values of K_1 and K_2 obtained from point by point fit of the data into equations (7) and (11) as average value. The standard deviations (σ) for the ionisation constants of amino acids are calculated using the relationship,

$$\sigma = \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - X_{av})^2}{N-1} \right]^{1/2} \quad (13)$$

where $X_i = K$ or pK , and X_{av} is the average value for K or pK . All calculations were made on a IBM-PC computer using program designed specifically for such calculation.

The thermodynamic functions were calculated using the equations,

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln k^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ$$

$$\Delta S^\circ = \frac{\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ}{T}$$

where, ΔG° is the standard free energy change, ΔH° the standard enthalpy change and ΔS° the standard entropy change.

Results and Discussion

The values of ionisations constants K_1 and K_2 are summarised in Table 1 at different ionic strengths and temperatures (which also include previous data⁸). The calculated values of both K_1 and K_2 showed little ionic strength dependence, hence an average value was calculated at each temperature and taken to the thermodynamic equilibrium constants K_1° and K_2° at that temperature (Table 2).

It is worth-noting that we can easily calculate the isoelectric point pI_s (pH at which the amino acid bears not net charge and hence does not move in an electrical field) for the amino acids at infinite dilution from the equation¹⁰,

$$pI_s = \frac{pK_1 + pK_2}{2} \quad (16)$$

Table 3 represents the isoelectric point data for the amino acids at which their structures are isoionic or zwitterionic. It is obvious that the isoelectric point depends on the temperature and lies in the pH range 5.34–6.08, and decreased in the order : pro. > (alanine) > ser. > phe.

The results for pK_1 and pK_2 reveal that pK_1° decreases in the order : ala. > ser. > phe. > pro., but, pK_2° decreases in the order : pro. > ala. > ser. > phe. The low value of pK for serine in comparison to alanine could be explained as due to the presence of the hydroxyl group. This is similar to that found when comparing 2-aminoethanol with ethylamine¹¹. The high value of pK_2° for proline may be due to the inductive effect on the secondary amine in the proline molecule¹².

It is possible to calculate the value of ΔH° by plotting $\log K^\circ$ against the reciprocal of absolute temperature ($1/T$); the slope of the straight line (obtained from linear least-squares analysis) is equal to $-\Delta H^\circ/2.303 R$. Then ΔS° can be calculated by equation (15). The plot of $\log K_1^\circ$ vs $1/T$ shows curvature, which is not unusual for the carboxyl group. The similar curvature was observed for the amino acids studied earlier⁸. For many carboxylic and related acids, the cause of this curvature has been discussed by Gurney¹³. But the plot of $\log K_2^\circ$ vs $1/T$ gives good straight line which reflects the high temperature sensitivity for the amino group¹⁴, i.e. the value of pK_2° decreases as the temperature increases. This systematic behaviour with temperature leads us to conclude that the second ionisation for the amino acid is the most effective factor on the

TABLE I—CALCULATED VALUES FOR pK_1 AND pK_2 OF THE AMINO ACIDS

Amino acid	Temp. °C	μ				
		0.07	0.12	0.17	0.22	0.32
pK_1 values :						
DL-Alanine	25	2.26	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25
	30	2.27	2.26	2.25	2.25	2.25
	35	2.24	2.25	2.24	2.25	2.24
	40	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24
	45	2.22	2.21	2.21	2.21	2.20
L-Serine	25	2.33	2.27	2.22	2.17	2.15
	30	2.40	2.26	2.22	2.14	2.09
	35	2.33	2.27	2.23	2.14	2.21
	40	2.20	2.08	2.01	1.98	1.94
	45	2.13	2.07	2.01	2.01	1.93
L-Phenylalanine	25	2.18	2.15	2.11	2.08	2.13
	30	2.22	2.18	2.15	2.14	2.14
	35	2.23	2.18	2.17	2.17	2.17
	40	1.99	1.95	1.96	1.96	1.97
	45	2.09	2.07	2.05	2.05	2.06
L-Proline	25	1.58	1.58	1.58	1.57	1.57
	30	1.59	1.58	1.59	1.58	1.56
	35	1.62	1.60	1.60	1.58	1.58
	40	1.61	1.59	1.60	1.59	1.59
	45	1.56	1.55	1.55	1.54	1.54
pK_2 values :						
DL-Alanine	25	9.71	9.71	9.66	9.65	9.61
	30	9.59	9.56	9.53	9.52	9.50
	35	9.45	9.43	9.40	9.38	9.36
	40	9.35	9.32	9.30	9.28	9.24
	45	9.21	9.18	9.16	9.14	9.10
L-Serine	25	9.19	9.15	9.14	9.15	9.09
	30	9.11	9.08	9.05	9.03	9.01
	35	8.99	8.96	8.92	8.91	8.88
	40	8.85	8.82	8.79	8.76	8.74
	45	8.71	8.68	8.66	8.64	8.61
L-Phenylalanine	25	9.18	9.15	9.13	9.10	9.07
	30	9.06	9.03	9.01	8.99	8.96
	35	8.94	8.91	8.88	8.86	8.83
	40	8.78	8.74	8.72	8.70	8.68
	45	8.67	8.65	8.62	8.60	8.57
L-Proline	25	10.65	10.61	10.58	10.56	10.53
	30	10.56	10.53	10.51	10.49	10.47
	35	10.43	10.40	10.38	10.35	10.32
	40	10.28	10.25	10.24	10.22	10.19
	45	10.20	10.18	10.15	10.13	10.09

Ref. 8.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC IONISATION CONSTANTS FOR AMINO ACIDS

Amino acid	Temp. °C	pK ₁ ^o	pK ₂ ^o
DL-Alanine	25	2.25 ± 0.00	9.67 ± 0.04
	30	2.26 ± 0.01	9.54 ± 0.03
	35	2.24 ± 0.00	9.41 ± 0.04
	40	2.24 ± 0.00	9.30 ± 0.04
	45	2.21 ± 0.01	9.16 ± 0.04
L-Serine	25	2.23 ± 0.08	9.14 ± 0.04
	30	2.22 ± 0.12	9.05 ± 0.04
	35	2.23 ± 0.07	8.93 ± 0.05
	40	2.04 ± 0.11	8.79 ± 0.04
	45	2.03 ± 0.07	8.66 ± 0.04
L-Phenylalanine	25	2.13 ± 0.04	9.12 ± 0.04
	30	2.17 ± 0.04	9.01 ± 0.04
	35	2.18 ± 0.03	8.88 ± 0.04
	40	1.96 ± 0.02	8.72 ± 0.04
	45	2.06 ± 0.02	8.62 ± 0.04
L-Proline	25	1.58 ± 0.01	10.58 ± 0.05
	30	1.58 ± 0.01	10.51 ± 0.04
	35	1.60 ± 0.02	10.38 ± 0.04
	40	1.60 ± 0.01	10.24 ± 0.04
	45	1.55 ± 0.01	10.15 ± 0.04

^aRef. 8.

TABLE 3—ISOELECTRIC POINTS FOR AMINO ACIDS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Amino acid	pI _c				
	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°
DL-Alanine	5.96	5.90	5.83	5.77	5.69
L-Serine	5.68	5.64	5.58	5.42	5.34
L-Phenylalanine	5.63	5.59	5.53	5.34	5.34
L-Proline	6.08	6.05	5.99	5.92	5.85

isoelectric point which varies in the same order : pro. > ala. > ser. > phe.

Table 4 presents the values of ΔH^o , ΔG^o and ΔS^o calculated for the two ionisation processes of the amino acids at different temperatures. It is obvious that ΔH^o has positive values indicating that the two ionisation processes of the amino acids are endothermic. The ionisation process for the amino group is more endothermic than that for the carboxyl group (about 5.54

for L-serine, 8.23 for L-phenylalanine and 9.57 kcal mol⁻¹ for L-proline). More heat is associated with proton ionisation from the ⁺NH₃ than from the COOH group. ΔG_1^o values have no sharp behaviour with temperature due to the independent ionisation of the carboxyl group on temperature, while ΔG_2^o values increase as the temperature increases. The lower values of ΔG_1^o for carboxylic group than ΔG_2^o for amino group, and the higher values of ΔS_1^o for carboxylic group than ΔS_2^o for the amino group, cause more spontaneity for the ionisation constant K₁ than K₂ (it is very sharp in L-serine which has more positive ΔS_1^o). These thermodynamic parameters indicate that the COOH group is several thousands times stronger acid than ⁺NH₃ group because the amino group of the α -amino acids increases the tendency of the carboxyl group to ionise because of mutual repulsion between the positive charge on the ⁺NH₃ group and the positively charged H⁺ ion according to the equation¹⁵,

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR IONISATION PROCESSES OF AMINO ACIDS

Amino acid	Temp. °C	ΔG_1^o kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH_1^o kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S_1^o$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG_2^o kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH_2^o cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_2^o$ kcal mol ⁻¹
L-Ser	25	3.04	5.00	-6.57	12.46	10.54	6.46
	30	3.08		-6.32	12.55		6.66
	35	3.15		-6.00	12.59		6.67
	40	2.92		-6.62	12.59		6.57
	45	2.95		-6.43	12.60		6.50
L-Phe	25	2.91		-0.16	12.44	11.19	4.22
	30	3.01	2.96	0.17	12.49		4.29
	35	3.08		0.40	12.52		4.33
	40	2.81		-0.46	12.49		4.17
	45	3.00		0.15	12.55		4.27
L-Pro	25	2.15	0.33	6.10	14.43	9.90	15.23
	30	2.19		6.15	14.57		15.44
	35	2.25		6.24	14.63		15.36
	40	2.28		6.24	14.66		15.23
	45	2.25		6.05	14.77		15.33

It is also obvious that the ionisation of the amino group is more enthalpy-dependent process than the carboxylic group.

It is worth-noting that our pK_1 and pK_2 are in good agreement with those obtained by other techniques (Table 5) scatterly reported in literature.

TABLE 5—COMPARISON OF RESULTS WITH THOSE FROM LITERATURE FOR IONISATION PROCESSES OF AMINO ACIDS AT 25°

Amino acid	μ	Present work		Literature		Ref.
		pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	
L-Serine	0.12	2.27	9.15	2.55	9.15	3
	0.22	2.17	9.11	2.29	9.12	4
L-Phenylalanine	0.00	2.13	9.12	2.09	9.08	5
	0.12	2.15	9.15	2.16	9.15	1
L-Proline	0.12	1.58	10.61	1.93	10.68	2

Experimental

The pH measurements were made with an Orion Research Ionalyzer 501 equipped with glass pH electrode (Orion 91-04) which was immersed in a double-jacketed cell thermostated at the proper temperature. The alkaline and acidic errors for the glass pH electrode were determined by making calibration as described earlier⁸.

L-Serine, L-phenylalanine, L-proline, NaClO_4 (all Merck), potassium hydrogen phthalate (Riedel), NaOH (Chempol), HClO_4 (B.D.H.) and Dowex-50 ion exchange resin (Dow Chemical) were used.

All the measurements were carried out in aqueous solution. Stock solutions of the required materials were freshly prepared. Deionised distilled water was used in preparation and dilution. Sodium hydroxide solutions were standardised by 0.1 M potassium hydrogen phthalate.

Procedure : A solution containing amino acid and sufficient amount of NaClO_4 to adjust the ionic

strength¹⁶ was thermostated at the desired temperature (25, 30, 35, 40 and 45°). The solution was then titrated with standard HClO_4 and standard NaOH separately, and the pH was measured after each addition of the titrant to determine pK_1 and pK_2 respectively.

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